

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A VALIDATED RP-HPLC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF
TOFACITINIB IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE
FORM**Kavali Shivakumar*¹, B. Raju¹¹Department of pharmaceutical analysis, Omega college of pharmacy, Osmania University, Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

A validated simple, sensitive, specific and precise RP-HPLC method has been established for the determination of Tofacitinib in API and pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatogram was run through Agilent C18 150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ using mobile phase comprising of 0.1% Formic Acid: Acetonitrile in the ratio 50:50. The flow rate was maintained at 1.0ml/min, temperature at 30°C. Optimized wavelength selected was 268.0nm. Retention time of Tofacitinib was found to be 2.314 min. %RSD was found to be 0.9. It shows linear response in a concentration range of 2.5-15 μ g/ml with regression coefficient of 0.999, %Recovery was obtained as 100.10%, LOD and LOQ values obtained from regression equation were 0.15 and 0.44. The method precision for the determination of assay was 0.6%. So, the method is effective in regular Quality check of bulk and pharmaceutical formulations.

Key words: RP-HPLC, Tofacitinib Tablets, Validation, Liquid chromatography, Bulk

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Please cite this article in press Kavali Shiva Kumar et al., A Validated Rp-Hplc Method For Estimation Of Tofacitinib In Bulk And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (11).

INTRODUCTION:

Tofacitinib belongs to the class of organic compounds known as *n*-acyl piperidines, containing an *n*-acyl ethanolamine moiety. It is FDA approved for treatment of autoimmune disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, and ulcerative colitis and Polyarticular course juvenile idiopathic arthritis¹. It is sold under the brand name of Xeljanz. Chemically, it is (3-[(3*R*,4*R*)-4-methyl-3-[methyl(7*H*-pyrrolo[2,3-*d*] pyrimidin-4-yl)] amino] piperidin-1-yl)-3-oxopropanenitrile, having a molecular formula of C₁₆H₂₀N₆, its Chemical structure is shown figure 1. It is solid white powder soluble in N, N-Dimethylacetamide, Methanol, slightly soluble in water, and very slightly soluble in ethanol².

Tofacitinib is a second degeneration selective oral Janus kinase inhibitor that works therapeutically by inhibiting the JAK-STAT signaling pathway to decrease inflammation response. By Inhibiting JAKs, It prevents the phosphorylation and activation of STATs. The JAK-STAT signaling pathway involved in the transcription of cells involved in the hematopoiesis an immune cell function³.

Fig 2.1 Structure of Tofacitinib

Tofacitinib can be detected by several techniques such as NMR, LCMS-MS. Simultaneous determination of tofacitinib and its principal metabolite in beagle dog plasma⁴, quantitation of tofacitinib, cabozantinib and afatinib in human plasma and urine⁵ by LCMS-MS methods. Determination of Tofacitinib in mice whole blood on dried blood spots Using LC-ESI-MS/MS⁶. RP-HPLC assay methods had been established for the estimation of tofacitinib in rat plasma⁷. Although the gas and liquid chromatographic methods have been realized as the most suitable. RP-HPLC techniques were developed for the Assay of Tofacitinib in pure form and in physical admixtures⁸, for the dissolution study of Tofacitinib in tablets dosage form⁹, for the quantification of the related impurities of Tofacitinib

citrate drug substance¹⁰, for determination of residue content of Tofacitinib citrate left on the surface of equipment used in the manufacturing process¹¹. A part of these, various analytical methods were advertised for the determination of Tofacitinib in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations¹²⁻¹⁵. Based on the above Literature survey, there are few methods for the Estimation of Tofacitinib. Therefore, an attempt was made to develop and validate a simple and economical liquid chromatographic method for the quantification of Tofacitinib. In present research work, RP-HPLC Method for the estimation of the Tofacitinib in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation has been established and validated using reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and reagents

Tofacitinib pure drug was obtained as a contribution sample from Hetero drugs Pvt. Ltd, Hyderabad, India. Methanol, Acetonitrile and Distilled water of HPLC grade and Phosphate buffer, Potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate buffer, Ortho-phosphoric acid of A.R grade were purchased from Rankem Ltd. Bhiwandi, Mumbai, India. The 0.45μ nylon filters were purchased from Millipore.

Instruments

The HPLC system- WATERS Auto sampler separation module HPLC 2695 consisted of a high-pressure pump and 10 μL capacity injector loops. The system was well equipped quaternary pumps, Photo Diode Array detector and integrated with Empower 2 Software for monitoring and processing of data. The analytical column used was Agilent C18 (150mm x 4.6mm; 5μm). UV-VIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T60 with special bandwidth of 2mm and 10mm and matched quartz cells integrated with UV win 6 Software was used for measuring absorbance. Other equipment like Electronics Balance-Denver was used for weighing of the materials. P^H meter- BVK enterprises, India, Degassing of the mobile phase was done by Ultrasonicator-BVK enterprises

Chromatographic Condition

The mobile phase comprised of Acetonitrile: 0.1% Formic acid in a ratio of 50:50 v/v and diluent consist of Water and Acetonitrile in the ratio 50:50. Samples were analysed using the following parameters. Flow rate; 1ml/min, injection volume; 10μL, run time; 05min, column oven temperature; 30°C and detection wavelength; 268.0 nm.

Method Development

Any analytical method started using reverse phase liquid chromatography as it is commonly used, and C-18 columns are also available. RP-HPLC method was developed for the estimation of Tofacitinib content in formulation. The mobile phase was selected based on the sensitivity of the process, the time necessary for the analysis, easily available solvents and simplicity of preparation. The mobile phase was premixed and filtered through a 0.45µm filter and sonicated for 10min to remove gases. Optimization of the mobile phase was taken based on various parameters such as retention time, the number of theoretical plates and resolution.

Solutions preparation

Diluent: Based up on the solubility of the drugs, diluent was selected, water and Acetonitrile taken in the ratio of 50:50

Preparation of Standard stock solution (100µg/ml): 5mg of accurately weighed Tofacitinib was dissolved in 3/4th of diluent in 50ml volumetric flask, sonicated for 10 minutes and volume was made up with diluent.

Preparation of Standard working solution (10µg/ml): 1ml of Tofacitinib stock solution was pipetted out into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent.

Preparation of Sample stock solution: (100µg/ml) 20 tablets were weighed, and the average weight of tofacitinib tablet was calculated, then the weight equivalent to 1 tablet was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask, sufficient diluent was added and sonicated for 25 min, finally the volume was completed and filtered by HPLC filters.

Preparation of Sample working solution (10µg/ml): 1ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Acetonitrile and 0.1% Formic Acid were mixed in a ratio of 50:50 v/v. The solution was degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes and filtered through 0.45µm filter under vacuum.

Procedure for method development under Optimized conditions

A mobile phase of Acetonitrile and 0.1% Formic Acid in the percentage of 50:50 % v/v was found to be the most suitable mobile phase for best separation of Tofacitinib. The mobile phase was pumped all through the Agilent C₁₈ column owning a length of 150mm x 4.6mm; and 5µm particle size with a flow rate of 1 ml/min. The column was at a 30°C. The column was

equilibrated by pumping the mobile phase for at least 30 minutes prior to the injection of drug solution. 10µl of standard and sample solutions were loaded in six replicates separately in injection port of the instrument and the area for the drug peak was measured. The detection of drug peak was monitored at 268 nm. The run time was set at 5 min. Under these optimized chromatographic conditions, the retention time for the Tofacitinib was 2.314min from the spectrum. From the peak area, the content of the above drug in ppm was calculated using the following formula.

$$\text{Assay} = \frac{\text{Sample peak area}}{\text{X potency of standard Labeled Claim}} \times \frac{\text{Standard Dil. Factor}}{\text{Standard Peak area}} \times \frac{\text{Avg. Wt of Tab}}{\text{Sample Dilution Factor}}$$

Stress Degradation Studies

The stability of analytical method was determined by conducting various degradation studies. 1ml of stock solution was stressed at different strain conditions by adding 1ml of respective reagents includes acid (2N Hydrochloric acid at 60°C for 30min), alkali (2N Sodium hydroxide at 60°C for 30min), oxidative (20% hydrogen peroxide at 60°C for 30min), thermal (by placing in an oven at 105°C for 6 hr), photo stability (by exposing to UV light in UV chamber for 7days), and Relative humidity (at 60°C, 75%RH for 30min) and neutral hydrolysis (by refluxing in water at 60°C for 6hr). The resultant solutions were diluted to obtain 10µg/ml solution and 10µl were injected into the system, chromatograms were recorded, and the assay for the degraded samples was calculated to assess the stability of sample.

Method Validation

The validation of analytical technique confirms that the characteristics of the method if they fulfil the requirements of the method. The Projected method was validated agreeing to ICH guidelines for system suitability, specificity, linearity, accuracy, and precision, limit of detection and quantification and robustness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Assay of Marketed Formulation

The chromatograms of both Standard dilution of pure drug and sample solution comprising 10µg/ml were recorded, the mean retention time of Tofacitinib was found to be 2.311 and the mean percentage purity of drug was 100.39. The results are shown in Table 1 and respective chromatograms are depicted in Figure 2 and 3.

Fig: 2 Typical Chromatogram of Tofacitinib From Standard solution

Fig: 3 Typical Chromatogram of Tofacitinib From sample solution

Table: 1 Assay Results of Tofacitinib Formulation

Injection No	Sample Peak Area	Standard peak Area	% Assay
1.	1767890	1794002	99.67
2.	1775927	1769910	100.12
3.	1782310	1772002	100.48
4.	1771645	1753365	99.88
5.	1787820	1771396	100.79
6.	1799210	1750261	101.43
Mean	1780800	1768489	100.39
S.D	11530.1	15714.4	0.6500
%RSD	0.6	0.9	0.65

Method Validation

System suitability

After equilibration of column with mobile phase, the blank preparation (twice) and five replicate injections of 10ppm of Tofacitinib standard solution were injected through an auto injector into the optimized chromatography process and the chromatograms were documented. The system suitability parameters were measured, and the results are shown in

Table 2 and the chromatogram is revealed in Fig.4. The results have been demonstrated with respect to %RSD, USP plate count and USP peak tailing. The %RSD for the five replicate injections was less than 2%.

Table: 2 System suitability parameters for Tofacitinib

Injection No	RT (min)	Peak area	USP Plate Count	Tailing
1	2.306	1794002	7028	1.19
2	2.308	1769910	7026	1.21
3	2.308	1772002	7016	1.21
4	2.310	1753365	7021	1.2
5	2.312	1771396	7221	1.21
6	2.313	1750261	7025	1.19
Mean		1768489		
Std.Dev.		15714.4		
%RSD		0.9		

Fig 4. A typical Chromatogram of system suitability

Specificity

The specificity of the analytical process was decided by injecting a blank (mobile phase), Tofacitinib and sample preparations into the chromatography system in the same experimental circumstances. The chromatograms were judged. The retention time for both standard and sample were identical i.e. 2.313min. it was observed from the chromatogram of blank that there was no interference at the retention time of Tofacitinib peak. Chromatograms are shown from Fig. 5.

Figure No 5. Chromatogram of blank.

Linearity

The linearity was assessed by measuring the peak area response of all solutions over the concentration range of the 2.5-15 μ g/ml in duplicate manner. Six concentrations were injected in replicate throughout the range. A linear correlation was attained between the peak response and concentration of Tofacitinib for LC method as proven in Fig.6 and was confirmed by the value of regression coefficient ($R^2 = 0.999$). The values are shown in Table 3.

Table: 3 Linearity data for Tofacitinib.

Linearity level	Conc. (μ g/mL)	Peak area
25	2.5	472839
50	5	888560
75	7.5	1355705
100	10	1789301
125	12.5	2233739
150	15	2683764
Slope	178198	
y-intercept	9790.4	
R2	0.999	

Fig No. 6 Calibration curve of Tofacitinib

Accuracy (Recovery Studies)

The Accuracy of the method was calculated through recovery experiments and was performed by spiking known amount of tofacitinib at Quantitation limit, 50%, 100%, and 150% of 10ppm in Sample Preparation. Each level was analysed in triplicate and % recovery was calculated. The recovery was found to be in between 99.17% and 100.70% and the results are summarized in Table 4

Table: 4 Accuracy table of Tofacitinib

Accuracy Level %	Amount Spiked (µg/mL)	Amount recovered (µg/mL)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	5	5.00	99.99	100.10%
	5	5.03	100.70	
	5	4.96	99.17	
100%	10	10.05	100.48	
	10	10.03	100.30	
	10	9.98	99.80	
150%	15	15.06	100.37	
	15	14.98	99.85	
	15	15.04	100.25	

Precision

System precision

It was assessed by spiking six repeated injections of working standard solution of same concentration (10ppm). The peak responses of tofacitinib were measured and % relative standard deviation was found to be less than 2.

Method and intermediate precision

These studies were evaluated by giving six repetitive insertions of performing sample solution of 10ppm. The peak areas of the analyte were measured and % relative standard deviation of was found to be below 2. The results of precision are summarized in the Table 5.

Table: 5 Precision Data for Tofacitinib

Injection No	Peak Area		
	System	Method	Intermediate
1.	1794002	1767890	1725503
2.	1769910	1775927	1718547
3.	1772002	1782310	1707234
4.	1753365	1771645	1719121
5.	1771396	1787820	1765381
6.	1750261	1799210	1721596
Mean	1768489	1780800	1726230
S.D	15714.4	11530.1	20125.7
%RSD	0.9	0.6	1.2

Limit of Detection and Quantification

The LOD and LOQ of Tofacitinib were evaluated by signal to noise ratio. These ratios are 3:1 and 10:1. Solution of tofacitinib was prepared in its strengths and injected 6 times. The detection and Quantification limits are 0.15 and 0.44. Chromatograms are shown in Fig 7 and 8.

Fig No. 7 LOD Chromatogram of Tofacitinib

Fig No. 8 LOQ Chromatogram of Tofacitinib

Robustness

Robustness of the method were established by finding the retention time of Tofacitinib under minor but purposely modified chromatographic conditions like flow rate, mobile phase composition and column temperature on lower and higher side of the original values. System suitability parameters were not much affected, and all the parameters were passed. The %RSD was within the limit. Therefore, the method was robust for estimation of Tofacitinib content and results are summarized in Table 6.

Table: 6 Robustness data for Tofacitinib

S.no	Condition	%RSD of peak response
1	Actual flow rate- 1ml/min	0.9
2	Flow rate - 0.9ml/min	1.6
3	Flow rate - 1.1ml/min	0.3
4	Mobile phase- 55:45	0.4
5	Mobile phase - 45:55A	1.1
6	Temperature - 27°C	1.5
7	Temperature - 33°C	0.6

Degradation Studies

There was no interference from sample, placebo and degradants peaks and Assay of analyte from each stress condition shows that all the samples pass the limits of degradation. Various stress conditions and assay results of the analyte are given in Table 7.

Table: 7 Degradation Data of Tofacitinib

S.NO	Degradation Condition	% Assay
1	Normal	100.39
2	2N HCl at 60 ^o c for 30min	94.02
3	2N NaOH at 60 ^o c for 30min	94.61
4	20% H ₂ O ₂ at 60 ^o c for 30min	94.46
5	At 105 ^o c for 6 hr	96.66
6	UV light for 7days	98.61
7	At 60 ^o c,75%RHfor 30min	98.76
8	H ₂ O at a 60 ^o c for 6hrs	98.92

CONCLUSION:

The RP-HPLC method is accurate, precise, reproducible, specific and stability indicating, and has been found to be better than previously existed methods because of its wide range of linearity, use of cost-effective and eagerly obtainable mobile phase, UV detection and low Rt. All these constituents make this method is appropriate for quantification of the analyte in unit dosage forms. So, the method can be productively used for routine analysis of Tofacitinib in formulations.

ACKNOELEDGEMENT

The authors express their gratitude to the management, Omega college of pharmacy, Ghatkesar for providing research facilities.

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